

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION, THE MOST
PRESSING ISSUES IN TEACHING NATIONAL GAMES AND EDUCATING
THE NEXT GENERATION.

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Annotation: *The article discusses the most pressing issues in the study and implementation of national games in terms of physical education in educating today's and future generations.*

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Thanks to independence, a wide range of prospects is opening up in the field of physical culture and sports, especially in the national games and exercises of the people, physical education classes in sports.

Regular and regular use of them gives good results and serves as an important factor in educating students to be healthy, energetic and strong. In the past, Navruz celebrations, festivals, weddings, which were attended by a large number of people, were not held without folk games, physical exercises, and national sports in general. Unfortunately, they have been completely forgotten and forgotten in the country, so it should be the duty of everyone who respects their people and nation to find and restore them.

From the point of view of physical education, their study and application is becoming one of the most pressing issues in educating today's and future generations.

In this process, to open a wider way to implement the Uzbek national games inherited from our history, to popularize them, to organize them in the family in preschool institutions, schools, recreation areas, various ceremonies and holidays; will inevitably have a positive impact on the upbringing of young people. National folk games have been widely used in competitions and debates since ancient times as an independent branch of folk ceremonies, rituals and customs.

Physical education has been formed in the traditions, customs and rituals of the people and has been developed and perfected for thousands of years. Folk

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

games The national games that have come down to us for thousands of years are "Riding on a horse", "Chasing a girl", "Goat", "Archery", "Chillak", "White bone", "Soqqa". , Like the Five Stones and other games, is an effective tool in the development of courage, agility, speed, balance, as well as the formation of posture, morality, intelligence, memory, attention, etc. is coming.

Indeed, the past of our people is steeped in the art of heroism and bravery. Because the competitions in such competitions as "Kurash", "Tortishmachoq", "Boron", "Mindi", "Turon" will be an important basis for the health of our nation.

It is difficult to imagine the peoples of Central Asia without horses. Because the horse is one of the idlers of the people's customs, weddings and entertainment. Horseback riding, archery on horseback, fencing, javelin throwing, horseback riding, horse racing, kid riding, and many other types of exercise are good examples. In the folk tales "Alpomish and Barchinoy", "Gorogly", "Kirgiz", "Kuntugmish" and others, the horse is described in full second place after the main character. For example, the concepts of a great rider, a sniper, and a mighty warrior were used in horse-related games. Umar Khayyam cites forty-two breeds of horses and gives a separate tariff for each. The People's National Games are one of the most popular public spiritual events in the national values. Navruz, Eid, weddings and various traditional ceremonies and rituals have long been celebrated without wrestling, kupkars (goats), races and many other national games. Such events are expressed in all types of folklore, in epics. They are interesting and fully described in the works of the great scholars Abu Ali ibn Sina, Alisher Navoi, Mirza Babur and later writers.

The world-famous Jizzakh's Karabayiri, Surkhandarya's Boychibori, Irkuki, Kok Kaptari, and Chambil Bellari are almost extinct. During the years of repression, horses were heavily taxed, resulting in some people slaughtering their horses and some giving them to the state for free.

In the recent past, and especially during the years of independence, the study and restoration of national games has led to their targeted use in the spiritual and physical development of students. The services of culture and art figures, well-known scientists M.Murodov, U.Karabaev, T.S.Usmonkhodjayev, R.Abdumalikov, F.N.Nasriddinov have been great.

Folk national games have several directions, in which dances, lapars, aytys, askiyas, and art of many genres predominate. There are also a number of action games and sports games that are inherited from our ancestors.

Almost all of these games are widely used in modern public holidays, competitions and weddings. The contents of the link are known to the public.

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

They are also included in many textbooks, monographs and popular scientific pamphlets.

Some educational games are also included in the Physical Education program of your secondary school and are popular among students. In addition, TSUsmonkhodjayev, F.Khojayev and a number of other authors created such collections as "Moving Games" (1963-1981), "1001 Games" (1991). Samarkand, Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Wrestling, kupkari-ulak, racing and various movement games are regularly used at large weddings in the mountainous areas and newly developed areas of Surkhandarya, Jizzakh, Namangan, Syrdarya, Tashkent and other regions. . These games are gaining popularity with the addition of blessings to the wedding, especially the interest of students in the national games, modern sports.

During the competition, the team, which took 1st-3rd place in the rounds, was awarded diplomas of the State Committee for Physical Culture and Sports of Uzbekistan and beautiful gold, silver and bronze medals. At the end of the Olympics, each member of the winning team received valuable gifts from our committee.

With the consent of the Government of the Republic and at the suggestion of sports organizations, it was agreed to hold the Olympic Games every two years.

Dedicated to the 1000th anniversary of the epic "Alpomish" in Termez ("Homeland of Alpomish") held national folk games, "Republican Festival of Alpomish Games." The 2000 Games were held in Faigona. The third festival was held in July 2002 in Gulistan.

Wrestling, horse racing, kupkari in the programs of the national competitions of national folk games (1991-1996) and republican festivals of games "Alpomish" (1998). (Capricorn), "Storm", tug of war, wrist strength test, "Mindi", forty stones (girls game) and other moving games. The opening and closing ceremonies of the Games and Festival were attended by local amateur artists, well-known artists of the republic, poets, cultural figures, writers of various fields, and it was held as a big celebration. Such national holidays and games have become popular because they demonstrate the rich, meaningful and high level of education of our national values.

It is well known that the role of women in our social and cultural life is invaluable. In order to commemorate the culture of ancient ancestors, to rejoice the spirit of the great ancestors of the past, in 1999 in Jizzakh, in honor of the Year of Women, "Republican festivals of the Tomaris Games were organized. This event was also held in a very uplifting spirit and was festive. Women's teams from all

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

regions of the country gathered and held competitions in gymnastics, athletics, sports, swimming and other sports. A similar festival was organized in 2001 in Shakhrisabz (Kashkadarya region).

It should be noted that the national folk games (Jizzakh, Termez, 1992), the republican festivals "Alpomish Games" (1998, 2000, 2002), "Republican festivals of the Tomaris Games" (1999, 2001) , 2003) and republican scientific-practical conferences. They covered the content of the national games. There were also many lectures on the role of national games in the content of national values and their educational significance. Their summaries were included in the scientific collections of the conference.

However, the issues of training young people in cross-country skiing, horse racing and other games are far behind. It would be expedient to establish equestrian clubs among the rural youth, to train them in equestrian sports from an early age, and to train young men of conscription age in military exercises on horseback. It should be noted that the two-part film "Alpomish" (directed by Usmon Azimov), made in 2000, fully reflects the content of national values. He described the practical work of "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" in wrestling, horse racing, meigan. Young people should draw good conclusions from this.

Different jumps, runs, and gymnastic exercises that are difficult to perform can be one of the most important activities in developing a girl's physical maturity if she is taught national movement game lessons.

It would also be a good idea to introduce the use of national action games as part of favorite action games and activities in families and kindergartens.

In conclusion, the national games of the people serve as an important factor in human development and the education of young people. For this reason, it is important to inculcate in students the socio-educational aspects of the national games.

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